

Pause, research, scrutinize, cogitate... but don't destroyIván G. Somlai¹

“Because each nation has its own history of thieving and lies and broken faith, therefore there can flourish only international suspicion and jealousy; and international moral shame becomes anaemic to a degree of ludicrousness”.

Rabindranath Tagore (1917)

Abstract

Since the December 2019 notice of the first case of a coronavirus pandemic, there emerged a contemporaneous and globally proliferating protest movement that spread to all 50 states of the USA and to many countries around the world, destroying statues. Often a person's complex history arouses contradictory understanding of past actions. Sadly, perhaps because of the complexity, we have seen only minimal efforts at conciliation and restoring civility. Now there seems to be sustained divergence between governments and corporate interests on one hand and disenfranchised, economically and racially discriminated, non-dominant others. The resultant social calamity considerably impacts adults, children, government and civil society in ways as yet difficult if not impossible to assess, as both the pandemic and protests relentlessly continue. We need deeper historical understanding through public education and acceptable plans for memorials.

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Introduction

It is natural that significant events, whatever they be and however they be described, are often caused by a complex array of concatenated elements that, in turn, contribute to often unexpected consequences. This refers to both natural disasters and social calamities.

Thus, in natural disasters, we recognize common overlapping aspects: health and safety; food; shelter; social protection; education; transportation, economic support and so on. A singular disaster, itself, may trigger succeeding devastation, such as flooding (including ash, mud and vegetative debris) and landslides precipitated by an earthquake or wildfire; or forest fires themselves caused by lightning. There are innumerable anthropogenically and technically induced catastrophes too.

Spatially and temporally distinct disasters, of any origin, may become circumstantially connected: *e.g.* peat fires in Borneo causing haze pollution in Peninsular Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand and the Philippines; Chernobyl nuclear plant breakdown sending fallout as far as Sweden and UK; a building collapse in Bangladesh killing hundreds of employees and disrupting a global chain of production; the Tohoku earthquake in Japan triggering a tsunami and causing the Fukushima nuclear reactor meltdown. The one common aspect to any source, origin or kind of disaster is the inevitable, massive social disruption.

Iterative changes in vulnerability as a disaster progressively changes—*i.e.* reduces, expands, increases, alters or joins another major event that, in combination, magnify certain outcomes. This illustrates the necessity to have comprehensive planning together with an improved culture of anticipation for potential consequential events.

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Similarly, sectoral entanglements may be made to significant and potentially disruptive social catastrophes, as we shall see in the following discussions. And therefore, I see parallels in that we should try to approach, understand and respond to the current severe societal tensions spearheaded by COVID-19 and Black Lives Matter (BLM) movement holistically, that is, by respectfully communicating and purposefully collaborating with all essential stakeholders; and by steadfastly persevering at meaningful change. *“Simply because change is slow does not mean change agents have to move slowly towards it”* (Brookings, 2020).

Present context

“Morally speaking, there is no limit to the concern one must feel for the suffering of human beings, that indifference to evil is worse than evil itself, that in a free society, some are guilty, but all are responsible.”

(Heschel, 1972)

The BLM movement, initiated in the United States (US) in 2013 and extended to the UK and Canada as well, has as its mission *“to eradicate white supremacy and build local power to intervene in violence inflicted on Black communities by the state and vigilantes”* (Black Lives Matter, nd).

This coronavirus pandemic has been contributing to massive unemployment, severe economic downturn, reduced remittances from abroad, increased costs of essential commodities, disruption of education, travel, tourism, commercial life as well as separation from family and public life. Beyond the general health impact of COVID-19, the especially inordinate impacts of higher infection and morbidity rates on the poor and on

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non-dominant minorities has served to highlight disparities in governance and social service delivery systems, challenging trust levels between the state and its citizens.

In one of many crackdowns on ensuing protests in the US, George Floyd was ignominiously and brazenly killed by a local policeman on May 25, 2020. This instantly catalyzed years of pent-up frustration in the Black community, supported by a great number of multiethnic and multi-background citizens tired of unresponsive governance, leading to the damaging or removal of statues across the country. Protests have been held in all 50 states against racism, white supremacy, and police brutality.

Unsurprisingly, like seeds blown by strong winds and germinating elsewhere, this impetus spread to other countries (*The Guardian*, 2020a) wherein locals likewise recognized similar issues in their respective histories and contexts, and felt the time to be ripe for proactive mass displays of dissatisfaction. Stimulated by each succeeding protest, localized reproductions speedily progressed around the world. Each event focused predominantly on issues related to historical wrongs committed on minorities. Expanding awareness of social and economic injustice had motivated people of all racial, ethnic, religious and otherwise different backgrounds to participate, for the most part, peacefully (ART, 2020).

Concomitant and collateral impacts

"What then is, generally speaking, the truth of history? A fable agreed upon."

(Napoleon Bonaparte de Las Cases, 1823)

Contributing to people's having time to protest during this COVID-19 pandemic have been the high levels of unemployment

and lengthy lockdowns, both availing time, despite the risk of arrest. Mixed messages from seemingly uninformed or unbelieving leaders allowed the proliferation of conspiracy theories, fake news and consequently, at times, the need find an outlet for frustrations. Further aggravating the tensions in some (usually democratic) countries were groups of people claiming to be “sovereign citizens”, outside of normal laws, therefore claiming their aversion to and inherent right to ignore precautionary government directives, such as masks, distancing, hand-washing, minimal grouping and so on.

For protest participants, technology has proved to be bifarious: while more people have been able to connect to others faster and disseminate more information to start with, increased electronic surveillance via cell phones has become regularized in many countries, often lacking clear understanding for the user, nor verifiable safeguards against abuse. As such, this technology threatens civil liberties and even fairness of criminal justice proceedings: *e.g.* to see who may have been in the vicinity of a crime, pinpointing a nearby cell phone user has led to innocent people being wrongly arrested, or labelled as criminals (Fair Trials, 2020).

While COVID-19 impact on minorities has been disastrous, it has been especially so among native populations. Having been rooted in a particular geographical area for millennia, autochthon elders' valuable knowledge is passed down through their oral traditions and culture and contributes to forming their indigenous society's identity and culture; when elders die prematurely before they have had a chance to teach what they know, historical memory of a people can be lost forever (BBC, 2020a).

The coincidental reinvigoration of the BLM movement, as a result of a police homicide of a Black American and other

flagrantly discriminatory acts against non-dominant minorities, has coalesced more people than ever to express dissatisfaction with the governance. Much anger has been levelled at statues representing disgraceful histories in the minds and eyes of non-dominant members of society.

Along with increasing protests, there was –and still is--an oscillating spike and remission in COVID-19 transmissions. The wearing of face masks by seemingly a majority demonstrated health consciousness, while it also prevented accurate facial recognition by police (NIST, 2020).

On the other hand, other public health experts have also made the argument that the goals of the protests may be worth the costs. “Over 1,000 health professionals sign a letter saying, “don’t shut down protests using coronavirus concerns as an excuse” (CNN, 2020).

These and other miscellaneous impacts of the current pandemic and the contemporaneous global antiracism manifestations are revealing the complexity of cogent government and civil society responses, with a pandemic exacerbating antiracism protests.

The remaining focus of this article is on the statues and other memorials being targeted by protesters. Starting with some illustrative laws, I shall then review the focus and impact of the widespread destruction-centred protests.

Illustrative jurisprudence

Various governments have laws and/or other supportive statements for preserving memorials, as shown by these three examples.

In denouncing racism and white supremacy, the European Parliament voted in a resolution to declare BLM. While this

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resolution has no legal ramifications, it does send a signal of support to anti-racism protests (DW, 2020a) from a highly visible and respected multinational body.

So as to safeguard humanity's cultural heritage, the United Nations Security Council Resolution 2347 was passed unanimously in March 2017 in response to the Islamic State's destruction of historic sites in Iraq and Syria. That resolution "deplores and condemns the unlawful destruction of cultural heritage, *inter alia* destruction of religious sites and artifacts, as well as the looting and smuggling of cultural property from archaeological sites, museums, libraries, archives, and other sites, in the context of armed conflicts" and states that such acts could constitute war crimes. Yet, despite the US being signatory to that document, President Trump had warned that "cultural sites could be targeted if Iran retaliates for Soleimani strike" (ABC, 2020; *The Hill*, 2020).

In some jurisdictions "*local governments have the authority to authorize the building of war memorials, but they are forbidden from removing, damaging or defacing them. That power rests with the state government*". But even some elected and appointed officials believe that it is based on an unsound premise (Irish, 2019).

The three examples above elucidate the following:

- a. The current protest movements resonate internationally;
- b. There are jurisdictions at all levels which have related regulatory directives;
- c. There must be clarity and specificity about any provisos to protective regulations;

- d. There is the need for clarified definitions and designations as to how particular statues could also be considered as “cultural heritage”;
- e. A common understanding need evolve of what constitutes any kind of memorial that deserves protection;
- f. There must be correlated maintenance, monitoring and enforcement capability; and
- g. Laws and resolutions imply acknowledgement of a perpetual challenge.

So now, on to the statues!

"A statue does not proclaim a truth, but encourages people to seek it,"

(Bernhard Ilg, Mayor of Heidenheim, Germany DW, 2020b)

Many events are emulated. Most recently, spurred by the BLM movement, demonstrations, protest marches and various forms of damaging structures have simmered and percolated across the world. In places, statues had been destroyed to counter perceived --or to purposely cause-- “*disruption (to) social and religious harmony*”, such as in Afghanistan and Nepal (*The Guardian*, 2001; *Nepali Sansar*, 2019; *Dawn*, 2020).

Collectively, we accept many aspects of dissatisfaction, because much of it is too obscure or wickedly complicated to pursue by all but those dedicated to extensive research and pursuit of solutions. So then, focus shifts to visible, physical representations of systemic weaknesses, especially during increased societal tension; and then, each concrete symbol demolished energizes those wishing to similarly act. Yet, statues are not the only simulacra of histories forgotten, repressed or revived.

Around the world, roads, canals, railroads and bridges have been built wholly or partially through slave or indentured labour; yet without a thought we continue to tour on them. Historical ruins, palaces and temples have been constructed with bonded labourers, thousands of whom have perished in the process; yet we travel great distances to behold and marvel at the beauty of such structures, few of which have any signs of contriteness. Fashionable clothing is fabricated in sweatshops by poor underpaid women and children in hazardous environments; and we, whilst browsing on Vancouver's Robsonstrasse shopping core, remain oblivious to this. Even the ubiquitous face masks have debatable origins (*The New York Times*, 2020; *Jamestown*, 2020). Why do these not elicit the same fervor for change as statues?

We are consumed by statues as they are visibly symbolic reference points.

I am not judging the correctness of attacking statues. No person who has used offensive language, communicated negatively about or expressed hatred of particular peoples, caused misery, famine, death and destruction deserves a podium. Anger is understandable. In fact, for thousands of years, adulatory sculptures have been installed and, at one time or another, defaced or removed. Even since the early 1900s, statues in Russia, France, Hungary, Greenland, Canada, Brazil, South Africa, Mongolia, Cameroon (*DW*, 2020c) among scores of other countries, have been either toppled by protesters or dismantled by government edict. Often such removals and, especially replacements such as in Thailand (*Crisis*, 2020), are unabashed efforts at rewriting history. That said, were we to seriously research the background of those represented in the statues or other memorials, many of us may be surprised.

The births of many modern nations had been initiated by the arrival of “western” interlopers or, as Nepal’s founding monarch Prithvi Narayan Shah is said to have quipped, those bringing bazaar, bible and *banduk* (*i.e.* trade, religion and guns to motivate obedience), leaving an undoubtedly confounding legacy! It would be exceedingly difficult to find a name or representation of one from any culture whom we could comfortably absolve of any and all atrocities. Thus, unless one prefers statues of only Mother Teresa, Chief Dan George, Albert Einstein, Greta Thunberg (*Times*, 2020) or Gandhi (though even that has been disfigured recently: *vide BBC*, 2015; *BBC*, 2020a; *The Telegraph*, 2020), almost any other historical statue will inevitably be of people who have had binary actions and impacts (think Genghis Khan; Mao Zedong; Simon Bolivar; Kwame Nkrumah, and even Nobel laureates like Nelson Mandela (*The Conversation*, 2020) and Aung San Suu Kyi (*The Atlantic*, 2019).

Many of the memorials erected have been for multipolar, compartmentalized characters with a record of welcome changes for some, but blood on their hands for others: *e.g.* one who helped liberate a country, only to then abet massive programmes of executions and famine to bring people to accept a “utopian reform” (Lenin and Mongolia); another, intimately involved in liberating a continent, while simultaneously allowing a famine to overtake millions on another continent (Churchill and Europe, and India); and the righteous ones with contradictory legacies in surreptitiously saving multiple thousands of persecuted citizens while simultaneously supporting (presumably and understandably for their own lives’ sake) the vile regime’s bureaucracy (*DW*, 2020d).

Then there were those who did unforgivable things from which, in the end, they personally profited. It is reasonable to assume that their decisions were calculated with knowledge of the

consequences: Hitler, Stalin, Pol Pot, Hoxa, Mugabe...the more infamous of the most egregious instigators, along with innumerable slave traders. Targets for mass killings and enslavement included those who were indigenous, or from a different religious, ethnic, racial, economic or political group. So, for those enmeshed in the purposeful planning, commitment and/or oversight of major atrocities, I have no sympathy. Yet many inbetween, such as Castro, Kagame and Mohammad bin Salman, have been implicated in contradictory liabilities.

It may thus be evident that difficulties begin when considering people who were basically well-intentioned within incredibly complex contexts, wherein their weighing of best alternatives sometimes resulted in decisions with deleterious impacts. So, were these errors of character, of fact, or of process? Were people purposely targeted and were people harmed or killed or allowed to die? Did they anticipate that there may be many people injured or killed? Would the then available alternative options have caused even more deaths and destruction? While a person may have done wrongs, had he (or she) also set in motion reforms that resulted in iterative –though not immediate--betterment of lives?

If we want to be part of a generation that makes an extraordinary effort to improve lives, we must demonstrate maturity in our ethics, morals and obligations to human rights with people of every race, religion, ethnicity, nationality, language and culture. From this manner of reflection then, protesters should decide: if the statue is an affront to current values, would it be best to deface it, bury it in a harbour or melt it down for scrap, situations in which no one may ever see it again? If so, many among us shall, or might, remain oblivious to particular gross wrongs committed and those who had been responsible for them.

Or would it serve a higher edifying purpose to leave it in place with an explanatory memorial tablet or remove it to a museum for posterity's historicizing? Rather than a statue to one who in the future might become embroiled in controversy, explanatory signs could be a proactive cultural option to memorialize a tragedy or famous event; however, the jurisdiction composing plaques must make a sincere effort to faithfully discuss input from the concerned groups so as to avoid lingering controversies.

Illustrations of alternative memorial management include the "Commission for Diversity in the Public Realm" established by London's Mayor, Sadiq Khan, to recommend which statues in London should be removed; and in Cambodia, a committee to designate historical battlegrounds as national monuments to teach younger generations about Cambodia's history (*Phonmpenh Post*, 2020). Discrete options already in practice elsewhere include Coronation Park in Delhi, where effigies of former officials from the colonial era have been relocated (*BBC*, 2020b); and the Spandau Zitadel special museum repository in Berlin, (Spandau, nd).

Many decades ago, an eminent lawyer and genocide historian stated that "*the destruction of a work of art of any nation must be regarded as acts of vandalism against world culture*" (Lemkin, 1944). In the same vein, South African artist and anti-apartheid veteran Pitika Ntuli, who spent decades in exile, maintains that a statue, even of an offensive individual, is a work created by an artist and, as such, 'should be put in a theme park', not destroyed, but as a reminder of colonial and racist history (*BBC*, 2020c).

A civilized option

Committing to a sustained dialogue would reflect acknowledgment of the need to confront colonial history. As a recent evocative example, children visiting a British colonial homestead in England “*came across stands depicting African men in chains – they had an important discussion about whether they should be on display. Some felt yes because it shows the house’s connection to the slave trade and the Royal African Company, while other children felt it was offensive*” (*ibid*). It is heartening to see such discussions initiated amongst school-age children.

Patient and respectful convening and supporting of exchanges between different sides should serve to elicit knowledge and empathy for each other’s views; and if, indeed, mutual respect and understanding could prevail, then it would be much easier to work on compromises and cooperation (Somlai, 2007).

A failure to recognize contestations in the past contributes to the politics of selective memory that is reproduced every time we evade our past instead of confronting it directly and truthfully (*University World News*, 2020). Of course, if the leader of an influential democracy repudiates the existence or severity of COVID-19 and calls attempts to rectify documented racist history by removing a statue as “bullshit” (*HuffPost*, 2020), this emboldens other populist heads of government to do likewise and therefore undermines conciliative efforts.

As far as names of any flawed benefactors on buildings, cities, streets and academic programmes, these could, indeed, be exchanged for contextually more appealing and appropriate names. Optionally, societies could consider shifting to a culture without person-based monuments to their heroes.

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Have we learned?

“It is our great opportunity today to shape our present action, based on our aspirations of the future rather than let it be governed by the baggage of hostility from the past”.

(Dr APJ Abdul Kalam, Former President of India, 2010)

Even if one could be reconciled to the aforementioned, we need admit that in every age and culture there have, indeed, always been upright people opposing maltreatment of others; human rights, even if differently expressed, are not an invention of our recent past. Sadly, in every age, disenfranchisement, hatred, vindictiveness, selfishness and exploitation have continued. Viewed in a historical sense, it can be said that we have not sufficiently learned from the past (*The Guardian*, 2020b).

Amongst millions of examples, perhaps the most poignant in the recent past were the photographs of two drowned migrant children—a 3-year-old boy on a Turkish beach in 2015 and a Salvadoran girl, not yet 2, on the banks of the Rio Grande in 2019. While having provoked widespread outrage, no lasting changes in immigration policy have been materialized (*National Geographic*, 2020)

In our “COVID-19 year”, the same photographer believed that images of coronavirus victims could “*force the public to take the lockdown seriously and hold leaders of various nations accountable for their response*” (ibid). Has that worked?

We need to realize that without a holistic approach and sincere collaboration, nor trust in respected scientists’ advice, just as a particular nation’s internal response remains uncoordinated and divisive, an international crisis does not necessarily lead to intergovernmental and global collaboration.

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Conclusion of remaining challenges

*The evil that men do lives after them;
The good is oft interred with their bones.*

(William Shakespeare from Julius Caesar,
Marc Antony in Act 3, Scene 2, 1599)

We have seen and felt now the coincidental, still evolving global cataclysms –COVID-19 and BLM protests--and their interrelated effects. Both have instigated awkward political controversy yet also inspired remarkable cooperation, or *samfundssind*ⁱ as they more precisely term it in Denmark, within and across societies.

This pandemic is challenging the brightest minds in all sectors, the most powerful security forces and all levels of society. Coronavirus will continue to be a proximate cause for delay and non-delivery of goods and services from previous months to the next few months (*TradeReady*, 2020), continuing to disrupt basic needs of communities. Economic contraction “*heightens the near-certainty that the pandemic will produce the first global increase in poverty since the Asian financial crisis of 1998*” (*Politico*, 2020). Major societal disequilibrium, along with an already coincidental and broadening protest movement, is expected to result in critical unexpected interactions that may yet exacerbate tensions and take peace and governance to *terra incognita*. At the very least, in many countries, trust will need to be rebuilt between government and civil society.

Altering, dismembering or stomping on statues or other representations, protesters transform their frustrations onto a rehumanized embodiment of their focus. But by doing this, are they not exemplifying a moral reaction obverse to their own desired ethical behaviour by others?

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Toxic outrage may force the elimination of symbols of racism and other atrocities, and it may likewise motivate proliferations of similar resistance to other displays of imperialism, colonialism and racism; but consequences may also include the realization of erroneous understanding of the subject; as well as counter reprisals in this “monument war” (*Global Times*, 2020).

One internecine after-effect in South Africa, attributable to black parents withholding painful histories from their offspring, has been that upon their eventual realization of past atrocities within a system of institutionalized racism, “*the anger of the young has pointed towards their parents and black elders. Over the course of the year, the young South Africans moved from throwing stones at statues of dead white men to throwing them at live black ones – President Zuma and South Africa’s education minister Blade Nzimande, who rose to fame as an anti-apartheid activist*” (*The Guardian*, 2015). What the older generation thought would be a blessing by not dredging up horrendous history, has turned out to be a curse for the present impatient generation not averse to confronting adversarial and immoral dominance.

We cannot blame the elders. This situation has analogies in other cultures and contexts: for example, many Jewish survivors from the Second World War have kept mum about horrid details to their children and grandchildren so as to avoid stress, enmity and any potential violence. Yet nowadays, there is a more confident, energetic and vocal generation prepared to counter persistent prejudice. In Japan, the Hiroshima Prefectural Office has recruited *denshosa*, or “legacy transmitters”, who volunteer to orally recount their experiences to survivors and visitors so that the evil would not be forgotten but that peace should prevail (*Japan Times*, 2020).

For those unconvinced that history could actually be forgotten, one need only refer to the relatively recent war in Iraq (2003-2011) and the superseding DAESH/ISIS terrorist regime (2011-2017), wherein the war and illegal trade of cultural heritage created an environment for illicit excavations, pillaging of museums, looting and burning of libraries, galleries and homes. In Iraq alone, 41 major cultural sites--oldest from the 8th century -- were damaged through wilful acts: 11 were completely razed; the rest ruined to varying degrees (OCHA-RASHID, 2017). Robert Mugabe, head of Zimbabwe until 2017, had condoned the state slaughter of thousands of his own people, referring to the massacres as simply a moment of madness and thereupon embarked on a programme of collective amnesia. Such is the intentional devastation of collective memory and identity. As noted by filmmaker Tim Slade, *“The whole point about erasure of physical trace is to allow you to pretend that nothing ever happened”* (Studio International, 2016).

Memorials can precisely serve the function of remembrance. The Hiroshima bombing sites, left in their haunted states, serve as effective symbols both of premeditated devastation as well as of the spirit of survivors. Either way, the memory endures. Statues could be considered in the same way.

Improving society is not *“about rewriting history, but it’s encouraging broader, evidence-based conversations about our past. We shouldn’t confuse national pride with history, which is always warts and all – history is full of violence and injustice, that’s nothing new”* (BBC, 2020b). Improving society must be undertaken as deliberately as the effort that detractors and anarchists expend in opposing democratic, orderly, equitable and cooperative society.

Thus, in the long term, it can be only deliberate, participatorily developed deconstruction and reconstruction of

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policy, regulatory improvements, governance, education and civic action that would gradually change the culture of attitudes and behaviours towards an increasingly equitable society. In this process, it is necessary to have the will and ability to look at a person's gore and glory and the contexts within which they took place, not so as to absolve hideous, maniacal and calculatingly evil individuals, but to enhance our collective understanding and knowledge.

I do acknowledge that there are limits to the level of systemic change achievable for a non-dominant group through peaceful persuasion. This is especially true for prolonged, morally justifiable efforts in the face of injustices—efforts that may have been undertaken for generations and reaching levels of frustration no longer restrainable (Somlai, 2016). The shocking discovery in May 2021 of 215 unmarked graves of native children in the Tk'emlúps te Secwépemc First Nation (Kamloops, 2021) has served to provoke action on simmering, unresolved issues of colonial enforcement. Had it not been the serendipitous use of ground penetrating radar, this may have remained hidden for generations.

Delay can be catastrophic. Many countries have gone through several iterations of regrettable, uncompassionate circumstances followed by promises, appeasement, accommodation, and even attempts at reconciliation. But as great a country as most of us indeed have, well-intended efforts can be stalled or forgotten. It is conceivable that unless past issues be seriously tackled, the cumulative effect of unresolved serious grievances may severely impede the progress of harmony within our society.

So, I favour decisions with adequate understanding of the antecedents of the disliked person represented in a memorial, and of the consequences of any actions which may elude the preferred

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education of future generations. At times, through historical research and/or evolving contextual appropriateness, we even have examples of reputation rehabilitations that satisfy contemporaneous morals, ethics and practices, such as Qin Shi Huang and Hu Yaobang (China); Pearl S. Buck (China, USA); Henry Morton Stanley (USA, Africa); Louis Riel (Canada); Emil Zátópek (Czechoslovakia); Saigō Takamori (Japan); and currently, even Joseph Stalin (Russia) within a societal seesaw of alternative memories (NPR, 2019).

As noted by former President of Israel Golda Meir in 1975, “*one cannot and must not try to erase the past merely because it does not fit the present*”. Rather we must take advantage of history, including unsavoury history, and keep it visible so as to enable enhanced learning from past misdeeds and errors by showing measured, humane, non-violent rectification.

Young and old alike must learn that there is not just light and darkness...but dawn and twilight as well.

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ⁱ Desire to do things for the good of the community